

Use of a new 3-hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4'-pyrazolyl]-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (HPCPB) as an analytical reagent for trace determination of vanadium(V)

Raj Kamal, Rajesh Agnihotri^a, Om Prakash* and J. R. Mehta*

Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, Haryana, India

^aE.I.E.T., Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, Haryana, India

E-mail : kamalraj_sharma@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Vanadium(V) in trace amounts forms an intense green 1 : 3 (M : L) complex with 3-hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4'-pyrazolyl]-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (HPCPB) in acetic acid medium (0.1 M) which is extractable into carbon tetrachloride and is stable for more than 3 h. Beer's law is obeyed in the vanadium concentration range of 0–1.4 mg mL⁻¹. Molar absorptivity, detection limit and Sandell's sensitivity when applying spectrophotometric determination at the wavelength of 410 nm, are 2.2×10^4 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, 5.48×10^{-5} g L⁻¹ and 0.0023 mg V cm⁻², respectively. The correlation coefficient being $r = 1.0001$. Ascorbic acid, dithionite, oxalate, EDTA and hydrogen peroxide interfere seriously in the determination. The method handles satisfactorily the analysis of various samples of varying complexity.

Keywords : Vanadium(V), HPCPB, determination, analytical reagent.

Introduction

Vanadium affects numerous physiological processes and biochemical reactions. However, vanadium deficiency consistently impairs biological function. Vanadium content in food is directly dependent upon the concentration present in soil. Once consumed, vanadium is stored primarily in fatty tissues, with the remaining amounts stored in the kidney, liver, spleen, or bone¹. High amounts of vanadium are said to be present in fossil fuels, such as crude petroleum, fuels, oils, some coals and lignite. Burning of these fuels releases vanadium into the air that then settles on the soil. There are cases of vanadium poisoning, the symptoms of which are nervous depression, coughing, vomiting, anaemia and increased risk of lung cancer. Such afflictions are sometimes fatal². Vanadium has also been reported as the index element in urban environmental pollution, especially air pollution³. Vanadium in environmental samples has been determined by NAA⁴, ICP-AES⁵ and AAS⁶. The first two methods are disadvantageous in terms of cost and instruments used in routine analysis. AAS is often lacking in sensitivity and is affected by matrix conditions of samples such as salinity. A number of catalytic methods having high sensitivity were reported^{7–10}. Catalytic solvent extraction methods

are highly sensitive but are generally lacking in simplicity. Several spectrophotometric methods for the determination of vanadium(V) have been reported using various reagents, but most of these methods suffer from a number of limitations such as interferences by large number of ions^{11–15}, heating and standing for a long time for colour development¹⁶ followed by extraction¹⁷ and lack of sensitivity^{11,13,18,19}. These deficiencies have encouraged the authors to develop a facile, selective, sensitive, accurate and reliable method for the determination of trace amounts of vanadium(V) using a new chromone derivative 3-hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4'-pyrazolyl]-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (HPCPB) as a ligand.

Experimental

UV-Visible (Shimadzu-140-02) spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used for absorbance measurements and spectral studies. A stock solution of vanadium containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ of metal ion was prepared by dissolving 0.2218 g of sodium meta-vanadate (A.R.) in deionized water to give 100 mL solution and standardized by ferrous sulphate method^{20a} volumetrically. Aliquots were suitably diluted to give 100 and 10 μg mL⁻¹ solutions. Solutions of interfering ions were

prepared by dissolving their A.R. salts in water or dilute acid to give $\leq 10 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$ concentrations. Acetic acid (2 *M*) was prepared by suitable dilution of glacial acetic acid (17.4 *M*). 3-Hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-4'-pyrazolyl]-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran (HPCPB) was synthesized by the literature method²¹ and dissolved in acetone to give 0.1% (w/v) solution. Chemical composition of (HPCPB) is $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ and its structure is

(HPCPB)

The spectral analysis of the compound is given as : IR (KBr) : 3278 cm^{-1} (-OH str.), 1613 cm^{-1} (C=O str.); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : 8.86 (1H, s), 8.25 (1H, dd, *J* 1.5, 8.1 Hz), 7.85 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.67 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.40–7.51 (7H, m), 6.98 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz) (Found : C, 69.62; H, 3.68; N, 6.62. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$: C, 69.40, H, 3.61; N, 6.75%). Yield 61%, m.p. 244–246 °C. Carbon tetrachloride (Ranbaxy) was used as such.

Procedure for extraction and determination :

To the sample solution containing up to $14 \mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}}$ in a 100 mL separatory funnel, were added 0.5 mL of 2 *M* acetic acid, 1 ml of 0.1% HPCPB in acetone and enough deionized water to make the aqueous volume 10 mL. It was then equilibrated once, with an equal volume (10 mL) of carbon tetrachloride for 30 s, taking care to release the pressure occasionally through the stopcock. After phase separation, the organic extract was passed through Whatman No. 41 filter paper (pretreated with carbon tetrachloride) to remove water droplets if any. The absorbance of the green extract was then measured at 410 nm against a reagent blank prepared under identical conditions. Finally, vanadium contents in various samples were computed from the calibration curve prepared under optimum conditions of the procedure.

Results and discussion

Vanadium(v) formed a green coloured complex with HPCPB in acetic acid medium, which was quantitatively extractable into carbon tetrachloride. It showed absorption maximum in the range 398–412 nm, where the reagent blank had also some absorbance (Fig. 1). The extraction showed a decreased trend in CH_3COOH , H_3PO_4 , HClO_4 , HCl and H_2SO_4 media. The decrease in extraction in the presence of strong acids may be due to the formation of oxonium salts of the reagent whereas in H_3PO_4 it may be due to the masking effect of excess phosphate ion concentration over the tolerance level. Therefore, CH_3COOH medium was preferred for further studies.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of V^{V} -HPCPB complex in carbon tetrachloride : Curve A = $1 \mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}} \text{ mL}^{-1}$ measured against reagent blank. Curve B = Reagent blank measured against pure solvent. HPCPB (0.1% in acetone) = 1 ml.

Vanadium(v)-HPCPB complex had been extracted into a large number of water immiscible organic solvents. The absorbance decreased in the order : carbon tetrachloride = benzene > dichloromethane > toluene > 1,2-dichloroethane > chloroform > cyclohexane > ethyl acetate > isoamyl acetate > isobutyl methyl ketone > isoamyl alcohol. Benzene, being carcinogenic in nature was not used for extraction. As carbon tetrachloride gave stable absorbance with a rapid and clear phase separation, it was selected as the most suitable extractant. The coloured complex of vanadium(v) with HPCPB formed under optimum conditions was stable for more than 3 h in carbon tetrachloride at 410 nm. A maximum and constant absorbance was observed in 0.06–0.24 *M* acetic acid

in presence of 0.8–2.4 mL of 0.1% (w/v) acetone solution of HPCPB at room temperature when the aqueous phase containing $1 \mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}} \text{mL}^{-1}$ was shaken with 10 mL (equal volume) of carbon tetrachloride for 5–120 s. The absorbance decreased on either side of the optimum range of these variables.

The metal complex obeyed Beer's law in the range 0–1.4 $\mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}} \text{mL}^{-1}$ and after this concentration it deviated from linearity. The Ringbom plot²² between log ppm of V^{V} and percentage transmittance showed that the optimum concentration of the metal ion, which could be measured most accurately, lied in the range 0.29–1.32 ppm of V^{V} . The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were : $2.2 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0023 \mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}} \text{cm}^{-2}$, respectively at 410 nm. The linear regression equation was, $Y = 0.438X + 0.008$ ($Y = \text{absorbance}$, $X = \text{microgram V}^{\text{V}} \text{mL}^{-1}$) and the correlation coefficient, $r = 1.0001$. The detection limit of the method was $5.48 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g L}^{-1}$. The ratio of vanadium(v) and HPCPB in the extracted species was determined as 1 : 3 by Job's method of continuous variations²³ as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper²⁴ for a two-phase system (Fig. 2), and also by the mole ratio method²⁵ (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Job's method of continuous variations : Total concentration (o----o) $[\text{V}]$ and $[\text{HPCPB}] = 1.963 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. Total concentration (•----•) $[\text{VI}]$ and $[\text{HPCPB}] = 0.982 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. Curve A = 405 nm; Curve B = 430 nm.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of various ions was studied in presence of $1 \mu\text{g V}^{\text{V}} \text{mL}^{-1}$ under the optimum conditions of the proposed procedure. The tolerance limits of anions/

Fig. 3. Mole ratio method : Total concentration of metal fixed = $1.963 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. Curve A = 405 nm; Curve B = 440 nm.

complexing agents added as their sodium or potassium salts after the addition of HPCPB (amounts shown as mg mL^{-1} in parentheses) were : Br^- , CH_3COO^- , thiourea (10 each), I^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , SO_3^{2-} (9 each), Cl^- , PO_4^{3-} , CO_3^{2-} , NO_2^- , SCN^- , sulfosalicylic acid (5 each), hydrazine sulphate (1), F^- , tartrate (0.05 each), citrate (0.01) and glycerol (0.01 mL) caused an error of $< 1\%$. The tolerance levels of cations were shown in Table 1.

Samples containing Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} and Ti^{IV} ions were masked by complexing agents as shown in Tables 1 and 2 and thus do not interfere. Ascorbic acid, dithionite, oxalate, hydrogen peroxide and EDTA formed strong complexes with V^{V} and prevented its reaction with HPCPB thus causing serious interference.

Determination of vanadium in reverberatory flue dust, high speed steel and synthetic mixtures :

Several synthetic (some of them analogous to palau and permendur) and technical samples such as high-speed steel super rapid extra 500 and reverberatory flue dust were analyzed by the proposed procedure with satisfactory results (Table 2).

The method was found to be simple, rapid and reproducible with a R.S.D. = 0.77% and compared favourably with the existing ones (Table 3).

Synthetic mixtures were prepared by mixing solution of vanadium(v) and other metal ions in suitable proportions so as to give the composition shown in Table 2. Reverberatory flue dust sample (100 mg) from copper manufacture unit was mixed with a solution of known vanadium content (1 mg) in a silica crucible and dried in

Table 1. Effect of cations on the determination of vanadium (1 µg mL⁻¹)

Cations	Tolerance limits ^a (mg mL ⁻¹)
Al ^{III} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Ba ^{II} , Ag ^I	0.5 each
Be ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , Sr ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Se ^{IV}	0.1 each
As ^V	0.08
Fe ^{III}	0.04
Bi ^{III} , U ^{VI} , Os ^{VIII} , Pt ^{IV} , Cu ^{II} , Rh ^{III} , Cr ^{VI}	0.01
Ru ^{III} , Cr ^{III}	0.008
Re ^{VII}	0.005
Pd ^{II} , Sn ^{II}	0.003
Ir ^{III}	0.001
Nb ^V , Ta ^V	0.0005
Mo ^{VIb}	0.03
Ti ^{IVb} , Zr ^{IVc}	0.01 each
Th ^{IVc}	0.005
W ^{VI d}	0.03

^aAmount causing an error not exceeding 1%; ^bin presence of 0.05 mg tartrate; ^cin presence of 0.5 mg phosphate; ^din presence of 0.05 mg fluoride.

Table 2. Analysis of vanadium(V) in synthetic and real samples by the proposed method

Comp. of sample (mg)	V ^V (µg)	
	Added	Found*
Ni (0.04), Pt (0.01), Pd (0.007) ^a	7	6.95 ± 0.68
Fe (0.018), Co (0.18), Mn (0.011) ^a	3	2.95 ± 3.04
Co (2), Ni (3), Mn (0.5)	10	10.07 ± 0.48
U (0.05), Re (0.01), Os (0.05)	5	5.00 ± 1.56
Cd (0.5), Hg (1), Ag (1)	7	7.16 ± 1.32
Ag (1), W (0.01), Th (0.01) ^b	4	4.07 ± 2.28
Cr (0.05), Pd (0.01), Pt (0.01)	5	4.96 ± 1.82
Mg (0.5), Mo (0.1), Be (0.5) ^c	10	9.84 ± 0.48
Zr (0.01), Co (1), Mg (1) ^d	5	5.18 ± 1.82
Reverberatory flue dust (100) ^b	10	10.00 ± 1.61
	5	4.96 ± 1.82
High speed steel super rapid extra 500 ^b	1% ^e	0.982% ± 0.48

*Average of triplicate analysis (mean ± %RSD); ^acompositions analogous to palau and permendur, respectively; ^bin presence of 0.05 mg fluoride; ^cin presence of 5 mg phosphate; ^din presence of 0.05 mg tartrate; ^ecertified value.

an oven at 110–120 °C. It was then fused with sodium peroxide (0.8 g). The fused mass was dissolved in 20–30 mL hot water and neutralized with concentrated H₂SO₄. Iron was precipitated as its hydroxide and separated by filtration. The final volume was made to 100 mL and aliquots (1 and 0.5 mL) were analyzed for V^V by the proposed method. High-speed steel super rapid extra 500 (0.1 g) was dissolved by boiling with minimum amounts of aqua regia^{20b}. Iron was precipitated as Fe(OH)₃ by adding 1–2 g of ammonium chloride followed by aqueous ammonia. The precipitates were filtered off and washed

with 1% ammonia solution. The filtrate along with the washings was heated to remove excess of ammonia, cooled and adjusted to 100 mL final volume. Aliquots (1 and 0.5 mL) were taken for the determination of vanadium(V) by the proposed procedure.

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Table 3. Comparison of the proposed method with some of the existing ones

Aqueous conditions	Solvent (λ_{\max} , nm)	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$) (molar absorptivity, $\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Interfering metal ions	Ref.
V ^V , acidic medium, benzohydroxamic acid	1-Hexanol (450)	0.012 (4.24×10^3)	Fe ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Sb ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Sn ^{II} , Ti ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} , Mo ^{VI} , W ^{VI}	11
V ^V , pH 3.5-4.5, picolinealdehyde benzothiozolyhydrazone, shaking time 10 min	Benzene (528)	0.0033 (1.54×10^4)	Fe ^{III} , Fe ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Pd ^{II}	12
V ^V , 0.7 M HCl, sodium sulphite, sodium acetate, 8-hydroxyquinoline	Iso-butylmethyl ketone (430)	0.0088 (5.73×10^3)	Zr ^{IV} , Al ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , Fe ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	13
V ^V , 0.0-0.5 M CH ₃ COOH, 0.1% 2-hydroxyacetophenone benzoylhydrazone in acetone	Chloroform (375)	0.0057 (8.93×10^3)	Fe ^{III}	18
V ^V , pH 6-8, dithionite, 5,7-dibromo-8-hydroxyquinoline	Chloroform (420)	0.006 (7.27×10^3)	Mo ^{VI}	19
V ^V , pH 2.0-4.0, 0.05% variamine blue (VB)	- (570)	0.003 (1.65×10^4)	Cr ^{VI} , Fe ^{III} , Ce ^{IV} , W ^{VI}	14
V ^V , butaperazine dimaleate (BPD), phosphoric acid	- (513)	0.0061 (1.05×10^5)	Cr ^{VI} , Ce ^{IV}	15
V ^V , 0.06-0.24 M CH ₃ COOH, 0.8-2.4 mL of 0.1% HPCPB	Carbon tetrachloride (410)	0.0023 (2.2×10^4)	37 metal ions do not interfere	Proposed method

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